

مراجعة کی مالی دستاویزات اور ان کا شرعی حکم

DOCUMENTING OF "MURABAHA" AND IT'S SHARIAH RULING

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ABSTRACT

Murabaha is the most popular and widely used method in Islamic banking. Which can be conveniently used for interest free commercial transactions. Murabaha means "selling at a profit or giving someone a profit on his property."

Murabaha is an Islamic business method in which the seller of the product explains the actual cost of his product to the customer and also explains his desired profit from above. If the true cost of the item is not disclosed to the customer or is concealed, then the Murabaha becomes invalid.

In this article, the different forms of Murabaha in which client's application, general agreement of facility agreement, local purchase order, Bank's instructions to the agent, confirmation of purchase, offer to purchase, schedule of payment of purchase price, promissory note etc. It has been mentioned in detail.

Keywords: Islamic Banking, Interest Free Banking, Islamic Business, Murabaha.

کلیدی الفاظ: اسلامک بینکنگ، اسلامی بینکاری، غیر سودی بینکاری، اسلامک بزنس، مراجعة۔

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